

DIVIDEND POLICY AS THE MAIN CRITERION OF ATTRACTIVENESS OF JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES

Ganiyev Sardor Murodulla ugli

Doctoral student of TSUE

+998977475741

sarikoooo@mail.ru

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Whether we like it or not, dividend payments are one of the important criteria that determine the investment attractiveness of joint-stock companies. Just as investment attractiveness requires transparency and profitability, there are principles that dividend policy should follow. They are as follows (Picture 1).

Picture 1. Principles of dividend policy¹

It is clear from the given picture that in the dividend policy of joint-stock companies, it is necessary to strictly follow the principles of transparency, clear term, distribution basis, fairness for all interested parties, consistency, development and stability through the growth of dividends. But we should note that the principles of development and stability are mutually exclusive. Because while stability means more of the same, development means financial growth.

¹ Sherkuzieva N.A. Increasing investment attractiveness by optimizing the dividend policy in joint-stock companies. Dissertation abstract written for PhD degree in economics. - Tashkent, 2021. - B. 21

Adherence to these principles also has a positive effect on the investment attractiveness of joint-stock companies.

In this regard, we refer to research from the perspective of the impact of dividend policy on investment attractiveness. According to Jae K. Shim, Joel G. Siegel, dividend policy is important for the following reasons:

1. Shareholders view the corporation negatively when dividends are reduced because they associate such reductions with corporate financial problems. In addition, when setting a dividend policy, management must identify and meet the objectives of its shareholders. Otherwise, shareholders may sell their shares, which in turn will cause the stock's market price to fall. Shareholder discontent increases the likelihood that an outside group will seize control of the company.
2. It affects the firm's financing program and capital budget.
3. Affects the firm's cash flow position. A company with low liquidity may be forced to limit dividend payments.
4. Equity is reduced because dividends are paid out of retained earnings and therefore debt to equity increases.”²

It is clear from the four mentioned aspects that the dividend policy serves as a means of confidence of shareholders and investors in the activities and prospects of the joint-stock company. Otherwise, there is a possibility that the opportunities for diversification of funding will decrease, and control will be lost. On the other hand, it is also a mistake to pay out the entire net profit as dividend. Because such financial decision-making and implementation can drastically reduce liquidity and solvency as a result of outflow of working capital. As a result, the investment attractiveness of joint-stock companies decreases.

We cannot say that dividend distributions are being paid satisfactorily after the mass placement of shares in Uzbekistan by Quartz, Ko'kan Mechanical Plant, and Jizzakh plastic joint-stock companies. This aspect in itself serves as a factor that further reduces the interest in IPO practices, which are carried out in terms of reducing the state's share.

The question of the effect of dividend policy on the price of shares of a joint-stock company is also a matter of constant attention of researchers and financial analysts. "Does a higher dividend decrease, increase, or have no real effect on stock prices?" Arthur J. Keown, John D. Martin, and J. William Petty conducted their research with the question.³

² Jae K. Shim, Joel G. Siegel. Financial management. USA. McGraw-Hill, 20007. – P. 337.

³ Arthur J. Keown, John D. Martin, J. William Petty. Foundations of finance: the logic and practice of financial management. Tenth Edition. USA: Pearson, 2020. – P. 440.

At first glance, the current price of the shares changes, taking into account the dividend expected from it. But there are still many different approaches in this regard. But researchers put forward three different scenarios for the impact of dividend policy on stock prices. They are as follows (Table 1):

Table 1
On the impact of dividend policy on stock prices scenario analysis⁴

Scenarios	Content
Scenario 1: Dividend policy is irrelevant	An investor is primarily concerned with the return on his investment regardless of the exchange rate difference or income in the form of dividends. That's why it doesn't always pay attention to the dividend. This aspect is more relevant to stockholders who trade on a short-term basis.
Scenario 2: Higher dividends increase stock prices	When investors are more interested in passive income, that is, in the form of dividends, rather than the share price, the share price will automatically increase. Because in conditions of high demand for an attractive investment stock, the supply is relatively low.
Scenario 3: Low dividends increase stock prices	If a large part of the obtained net profit is reinvested in order to implement a prospective project, and if the project is predicted by investors to be very promising and will bring high profits in the future, then the share price will increase.

The investment attractiveness of joint-stock companies is also demonstrated by the category of listing on the stock exchange. On the other hand, the imposition of listing requirements for self-regulation of the stock exchange is not without reason (Table 2).

Table 2
Tashkent RFB Premium category listing requirements⁵

№	Request name	Specified demand
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⁴ Compiled by the author

⁵ Положение о биржевом котировальном листе республиканской фондовой биржи «Тошкент». Решение Наблюдательного Совета АО РФБ «Тошкент» Протокол №1 от 09.07.2020 г.

1	Capital	15 billion soums and more at the time of submission of documents
2.	Activity as a joint-stock company	More than 5 years
3.	Free swimming	More than 15%
4.	Audit organization	Availability of internal audit
5.	Department of Corporate Governance	Mandatory
6.	Financial reporting standards	Financial reporting and auditing based on International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS or GAAP) and International Auditing Standards (ISA).
7.	Existence of the corporate governance code approved by the general meeting of shareholders of the issuer	Mandatory
8.	Number of shareholders	At least 300 shareholders
9.	Presence of a corporate website	Mandatory
10.	Net profit	At least 10% of the authorized capital every year
11.	Dividend payment	Stability of dividend payments – at least 30% of net profit annually for the last 3 years
12.	Presence of an independent member of the Supervisory Board	Mandatory
13.	Liquidity of securities	The presence of a market maker or the requirement that the number of trading days during which transactions with these securities are concluded on the exchange is at least 70% of the number of trading days for the previous year.
14.	Financial indicators	- Return on assets: $RA > 0.1$ - Coverage ratio (solvency): $CR > 2$ - Coefficient of financial independence: $CFI > 0.5$

If we pay attention to the listing requirements of the Premium category of the "Tashkent" republican stock exchange, the stability of paying dividends is set as a special requirement, and in this case, at least 30% of the net profit for the last three financial years must be allocated to dividends, and this requirement must be continuously observed in the following years. This aspect in itself also serves the confidence of investors.

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